

Data management plan for “Development of real-time monitoring methodology for ship diesel engines with the aim of increasing energy and ecological efficiency using non-destructive testing methods” project New

Version 1

Description

The research objective is to develop a methodology for monitoring ship power systems-diesel engines, based on the method of non-destructive testing and diagnostics. The following tasks will be carried out:

1. Analysis of the main kinds and the nature of operational defects of engines. Identification of monitoring objects. Analysis of the existing approaches to predicting engine life cycles.
2. Analysis and evaluation of the effectiveness of existing engine monitoring systems and condition based on maintenance of engines. Analysis of the existing approaches to assess engine reliability and their maintenance cycle predictions;
3. Evaluation of test possibility of ship engines; selection and justification of diagnostic methods and corresponding informative parameters. Preparation and submission of project proposal to Horizon Europe call for proposals;
4. Development of diagnostic models and diagnostic algorithms of engines, their systems, components and parts. Development of monitoring methodology, experimental studies and diagnostic tests for engines and their systems. Preparation of two publications together with collaboration scientist from Texas A&M University

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Development of real-time monitoring methodology for ship diesel engines with the aim of increasing energy and ecological efficiency using non-destructive testing methods

Researchers

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Organizations

Riga Technical university, Faculty of Civil and Mechanical Engineering, Aeronautics, Space Engineering and Transport Institute

1. Main Info

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Organizations:

Riga Technical university, Faculty of Civil and Mechanical Engineering, Aeronautics, Space Engineering and Transport Institute

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Development of real-time monitoring methodology for ship diesel engines with the aim of increasing energy and ecological efficiency using non-destructive testing methods

Project:

3. License

License:

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2024-12-16

4. Templates

Descriptions

Research data

Šis zinātniskās literatūras apskats ir veltīts akustiskās emisijas (AE) metodes pielietojanas jomu un iespējām analizēt dažādus defektus un uzraudzīt kuģu dīzeļdzinējus. Mehāniskie bojājumi rodas, veidojoties un augot līdz kritiskam līmenim noguruma plaisām dažādās dīzeļdzinēja detaļās.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

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1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Šis zinātniskās literatūras apskats ir veltīts akustiskās emisijas (AE) metodes pielietošanas jomu un iespējām analizēt dažādus defektus un uzraudzīt kuģu dīzeļdzinējus. Mehāniskie bojājumi rodas, veidojoties un augot līdz kritiskam līmenim noguruma plaisām dažādās dīzeļdzinēja detaļās. Akustiskās emisijas metodes vispārējā teorija ir izklāstīta darbos [1, 10, 53], kur apskatīta akustisko metožu izmantošana defektoskopijā un metālu fizikāli-mehānisko īpašību kontrolē. AE metodes defektu monitoringa metodoloģija ir izklāstīta darbos [2–4], taču izstrādātā metodoloģija attiecas uz kompozītmateriāliem, kas prasa tās pielāgošanu metāla kuģu dīzeļdzinēju detaļām.

Ņemot vērā, ka daudzas detaļas dīzeļdzinējos tiek ražotas metinot un liejot, tajās var veidoties un attīstīties noguruma plaisas, kas var novest pie defektu rašanās. Metināto savienojumu monitoringa jautājumi ir apskatīti darbos [5, 8, 12, 39, 42]. Taču šajos darbos analizētie objekti nav saistīti ar kuģu dzinējiem, kas prasa papildu pētījumus.

Atsevišķu iekšdedzes dzinēja elementu, kas ietekmē tā stabilu darbību, piemēram, cauruļvadu, virzuļa gredzenu, sprauslu u.c., stāvokļa pētījumi, izmantojot AE metodi, ir izklāstīti darbos [9, 11, 13–18, 20, 32]. Šie darbi apstiprina, ka kuģu dzinēju stāvokļa uzraudzība un bojājumu atklāšana ir iespējama ar AE metodi, kā arī ar vibrācijas metodi [27, 40], kas līdz šim ir bijusi galvenā dzinēja stāvokļa monitoringa metode. Jāatzīmē, ka AE metode neizslēdz papildu izpēti metožu izmantošanu, lai iegūtu pilnīgāku un uzticamāku bojājumu monitoringa rezultātu.

Noguruma mikroplaisu veidošanās un to turpmākās izaugsmes pētījumi metāla konstrukcijās, piemēram, dzelzceļa vagonos, izmantojot AE metodi, ir aplūkoti darbā [19]. Saistībā ar dzelzceļu zinātniskajā rakstā [55] ir aplūkots jautājums par dzelzceļa sliežu ceļu monitoringu pārmijās, izmantojot sensoru metodi, kuras pamatā ir akustiskā emisija. Arī darbā [26] tika pētīts jautājums par noguruma plaisu rašanās un augšanas noteikšanu, izmantojot AE metodi. Šī pieeja

pētījumiem ļauj to izmantot detaļu ekspluatācijas robežu noteikšanā un kuģu dzinēju monitoringa procesā.

AE metodes izmantošana dažādu mehānismu un dīzeļdzinēju bojājumu monitoringā ir aplūkota darbos [21, 22, 29, 30, 36, 41, 43, 56, 57]. Minētās publikācijas apstiprina izvēlētajās pieejas pareizību kuģu dzinēju monitoringa un bojājumu noteikšanas uzdevumu risināšanā. Tomēr joprojām aktuāls ir jautājums par AE signālu mērījumu rezultātu reģistrācijas un analīzes organizēšanu.

Jauns virziens mehānismu ar rotējošām daļām bojājumu noteikšanā ir rotējošo detaļu momentānā leņķiskā ātruma noteikšanas metode [23, 49, 52]. Piemēram, darbā [25] šī pieeja tika izmantota četraktu četrcilindru dīzeļdzinēja kloķvārpstas vērpes svārstību pētījumos. Tiek apgalvots, ka šī monitoringa metode ir vienkāršāka un ērtāka nekā AE vai vibrācijas mērījumu metodes. Tajā pašā laikā darbā [24] ir aprakstīta pieeja, kā noteikt dīzeļdzinēja kloķvārpstas vērpes svārstības, izmantojot diskretu atsperes un koncentrētās masas modeli un galīgo elementu modeli. Tomēr dažādu monitoringa metožu kombinācija ļauj uzlabot mehānisma darbības prognozēšanas uzticamību un precizitāti.

Mūsdienīgas pieejas pētījumiem ļauj analizēt AE metodes mērījumu rezultātus, lai lokalizētu defektus, izmantojot augstas precizitātes neironu un grafu tīklus [28]. Tas uzlabo prognožu precizitāti un uzticamību, kā arī samazina laiku, kas nepieciešams mērījumu rezultātu apstrādei un analīzei. Turklāt darbos [33–35] ir apskatīta AE signālu mērījumu rezultātu apstrādes metode, izmantojot šo signālu kartēšanu.

Viens no svarīgākajiem pētniecības virzieniem lieljaudas dīzeļdzinēju jomā ir troksņa samazināšana, kas rodas no strādājošiem mehānismiem. Šis jautājums ir aplūkots darbā [31], kurā norādīts iespējamais problēmas risinājums, mainot mehāniskās ierosmes struktūru. Troksņa samazināšana vienlaikus samazina dzinēja vibrācijas, kas uzlabo tā darbības stabilitāti.

Viens no galvenajiem mehānisko konstrukciju degradācijas mehānismiem ir korozijas izraisīts nogurums [37, 38]. Minētajos darbos ir apskatīta korozijas noguruma bojājumu atklāšana un monitorings, izmantojot bezkontakta AE metodi. Šī pieeja tiek uzskatīta par perspektīvu konstrukciju izpēti un

monitoringa risinājumu. Bezkontakta AE sensoru izmantošana ļauj veikt mērījumus, nepārtraucot un neapgrūtinot darba telpu ap kuģa dīzeļdzinēju, lai gan minētajos darbos mērījumi tika veikti ūdens vidē.

Saskaņā ar publikācijām [44–46] AE metodi var izmantot, lai reģistrētu noguruma plaisu rašanos un izaugsmi izstrādājumos, kas izgatavoti no dažādiem materiāliem, piemēram, metāliem, kompozītmateriāliem u.c. Turklāt ar AE metodi ir iespējams veikt materiālu, tostarp kompozītmateriālu, monitoringu augstās temperatūrās [48]. Šis apstāklis ievērojami paplašina AE metodes pielietošanas iespējas.

Viena no svarīgākajām AE metodes pielietošanas problēmām ir signālu no sensoriem apstrādes sarežģītība. Jāņem vērā, ka AE signālu sensori ir nelineāri. Darbā [47] ir aplūkota normalizācijas metode, kas ļauj pārvarēt ilgi pastāvējušo AE sensoru nelinearitātes problēmu. Papildus tam darbā [50] tiek apskatīti vāji AE signāli un to apstrādes un analīzes metodes.

Iekšdedzes dzinēju stāvokļa monitoringa var tikt veikts ne tikai ar nesagraujošās kontroles metodēm, tostarp AE metodi, bet arī analizējot smērēļļu [51] vai izmantojot vizuālos ferogrāfus [54].

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Textual data
- Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- PNG

- XLS

- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No, the data collected in the project will be newly generated, specifically tailored for the development of the innovative engine monitoring method.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data will benefit

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Yes, an embargo period is planned until the publication of related research articles. This will ensure proper academic acknowledgement.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

Data will be deposited in Zenodo, a trusted open-access repository

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Data will be accessible through standard software tools like Microsoft Excel, Word, Adobe Reader for PDFs.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Yes, all data formats (e.g., CSV, XLS, PDF) are widely recognized open formats that can be used with multiple software applications.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Yes, the project will use material and measurement standards.

2.3.3 Other relevant remarks

The project emphasizes compliance with FAIR principles to maximize data compatibility and usability across various domains.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

CC0 1.0

The project ensures that data is well-documented, openly accessible (where applicable), and compliant with standards for interoperability. Metadata, clear versioning, and keywords will make the data findable and reusable by researchers, industries, and educators. Embargo periods will be clearly defined, and access methods will be streamlined to encourage broad re-use.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-01-29

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Yes. Data quality assurance will be ensured through:

Regular Validation: Experimental data will be validated using established scientific methods and cross-checked against controls.

Standardized Procedures: Data collection and processing will follow standardized protocols to minimize errors.

Review and Audits: Periodic reviews and audits by project team members will verify data integrity and consistency.

Use of Reliable Tools: Analytical tools and software with proven accuracy will be employed to process and analyze the data.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Costs for making data FAIR during the project will be covered through:

Project Budget Allocation: A dedicated portion of the project budget will be allocated for data management activities, including FAIR compliance.

External Funding: Costs related to repository fees (e.g., Zenodo), data curation, and management tools will be included in the funding application.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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The project leader will oversee data management responsibilities, supported by a dedicated data manager. Specific tasks include:

Data Collection: Assigned to researchers conducting experiments.

Data Processing and Analysis: Handled by researchers with support from the data manager.

Metadata Creation and Documentation: Led by the data manager, ensuring adherence to standards.

Data Storage and Security: IT support staff will manage secure data storage and backup solutions.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Institutional Support: Hosting and maintaining data repositories through institutional infrastructure.

Open Access Funding: Costs associated with long-term data preservation and accessibility will be covered through institutional open access initiatives or by seeking external grants.

Collaborative Agreements: Partner organizations may contribute to sustaining FAIR data practices.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

- Physical access control

Security Measures Include:

Data Encryption: All sensitive and experimental data will be encrypted both in transit and at rest.

Access Control: Role-based access controls (RBAC) will limit access to authorized personnel only.

Regular Backups: Automated, encrypted backups will be maintained in geographically redundant locations.

Firewall and Antivirus Systems: Institutional IT systems will ensure network security and protection against potential cyber threats.

Application of Security Measures:

Encrypted storage will be applied on institutional servers.

Researchers will use secure data transfer protocols (e.g., SFTP) when sharing data.

Periodic audits will ensure compliance with security policies.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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